

Low-noise supercontinuum in a normal dispersion ZBLAN fibre employing a pump with cascaded compression

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Supercontinuum (SC) generated in an all-normal dispersion polarisation-maintaining (PM) fibre with a femtosecond (fs) pump can have a smooth spectral intensity while preserving a single pulse in the time domain. In addition, these SCs can exhibit ultra-low pulse-to-pulse fluctuation [1] that enables a number of applications. In the near-infrared, such low-noise sources based on silica fibres have been used in demonstrations of shot-noise-limited SC-based ultra-high-resolution optical coherence tomography [2].

In this work we have developed a low-noise mid-infrared (MIR) SC source using a PM $6.7 \times 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ core ZBLAN fibre with a dispersion measured to be normal until $3.75 \mu\text{m}$. We started with a $1.55 \mu\text{m}$ 110 fs laser with a repetition rate of 40 MHz and a hybrid fibre made of PM1550-XP and PM2000D fibres to generate a low-noise SC spanning $0.9\text{--}2.1 \mu\text{m}$ as was done in Ref. [1]. We then amplified the $1.7\text{--}2.0 \mu\text{m}$ part of this SC in a thulium-doped amplifier [3]. The output of the thulium-doped amplifier was compressed to 58 fs using a PM1500-XP fibre. The average power was 210 mW. As the bandwidth of the SC out of the normal dispersion ZBLAN fibre scales with the input peak power, we then soliton compressed the pulse further in 1.6 cm of a PM and highly nonlinear fibre (PMHN5), as demonstrated in Ref. [4] using a different fibre. Simulations showed that the soliton compression should result in a close-to-single-cycle pulse.

Fig. 1: Simulated (a) and measured (b) spectral evolution along the length of PMHN5 fibre. (c) Measured spectra and the RIN out of the $6.7 \times 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ elliptical core ZBLAN fibre.

The simulated and experimental spectra along the length of PMHN5 fibre are shown in Figs. 1(a) and (b), respectively. Numerically the point of maximum compression is found to be at 1.2 cm, which is reasonably close to the measured 1.6 cm (see dashed lines). We measured the pulse-to-pulse relative intensity noise (RIN) of the sub-10 fs pulse to be 0.52% using an electronic spectrum analyser. The short pulse was coupled into one of the fundamental modes of the $6.7 \times 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ core ZBLAN fibre. The low-noise spectra spans $0.780\text{--}2.715 \mu\text{m}$ at the -30 dB level and is shown in Fig. 1(c) along with the spectrally resolved RIN. The measured RIN is as low as 0.21% at $2.1 \mu\text{m}$.

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